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Research Article

**DEPRESSION AND ANXIETY IN PATIENTS WITH
HYPOTHYROIDISM**¹Dr. Majid Ali Soomro, ¹Dr. Salma Kadir, ¹Dr. Bedar Bakhat Khan,³Dr. Shumaila Khalil, ³Dr. Samar Raza and ¹Muhammad Jan Khetran¹Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences (LUMHS) Jamshoro, ²Zulekha Hospital
Dubai United Arab Emirates, ³Liaquat University Hospital Hyderabad / Jamshoro**Article Received:** June 2019 **Accepted:** July 2019 **Published:** August 2019**Abstract:****Objective:** To determine the frequency of depression and anxiety in patients with hypothyroidism**Patients And Methods:** A total of fifty patients known case of hypothyroidism were included in the study. The criterion for the selection of the patients for the study was those patients diagnosed case of hypothyroidism, of >18 year of age and either gender. The demographical and clinical profile of subjects was also noted. The comorbidities were also explored while the thyroid profile was also explored through clinical history, physical examination and specific investigations. The Hamilton depression and anxiety rating scales were used to detect the depression and anxiety whereas the frequency / percentages (%) and means $\pm$ SD compute d for study variables.**Results:** During six month study period total fifty patients had anxiety and depression was explored and study. The mean $\pm$ SD for age (yrs) of population was 49.88 ± 6.32 . Regarding gender distribution male 20 (40%) and female 30 (60%) while the psychiatric illness anxiety 15 (30%) and depression 13 (26%) whereas the marital status reported as married 35 (70%) and single 15 (30%). The severity of depression was identified as mild 06 (46.1%), moderate 04 (30.7%) severe 03 (23.0%) and anxiety as mild 07 (46.6%), moderate 06 (40.0%) and severe 02 (13.3%) respectively.**Conclusion:** Thyroid hormones assume to be a significant job in state of mind and conduct, and perception is a built up element.**KeyWords:** Anxiety, depression and hypothyroidism.**Corresponding author:****Muhammad Jan Khetran,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Thyroid dysfunctions have been perceived to cause huge indications in psychological well-being. They may prompt unsettling influences in feelings and insight [1]. Both increment and abatement in thyroid capacity can cause state of mind irregularities. The other way around, gloom can likewise go connected at the hip with unpretentious thyroid dysfunctions [2]. Mental signs normally seem first in instances of hypothyroidism. They structure around 2–12% of the underlying side effects in pretty much the majority of the announced cases [3]. At first, it begins with uneasiness, memory slips, dynamic mental easing back, and discourse shortages. Evaluation of the thyroid capacity tests can be a decent indicator in the treatment of depression and bipolar disorders. [4] THs can be utilized as growth specialists and are restoratively productive in treatment-safe gloom. One theory expressed that TH balances postsynaptic beta-adrenergic receptors in cerebral cortex and cerebellum while others expressed that the balance of 5-HT and its receptors is capable, which occurs because of hindrance brought about by the thyroid hormone at raphe, causing decrease in 5-HT levels [5]. Subsequently this study tended to the anxiety and depressive manifestations in patients with hypothyroidism in health care setup of developing country.

PATIENT AND METHODS:

A total of fifty patients known case of hypothyroidism were included in the study. The criterion for the selection of the patients for the study was those patients diagnosed case of hypothyroidism, of >18 year of age and either gender. The exclusive criteria were known patients of hyperthyroidism, known case of anxiety and psychosis, already on anti psychotic and anti depressants, thyroid malignancy or on immune-suppressive therapy or anti arrhythmic therapy, known cases of chronic viral hepatitis and pregnant and lactating ladies. After having selected cases for the study, careful history & physical examination was carried out in each patient in particular relation to thyroid examination. The demographical and clinical profile of subjects was also noted. The co-morbidities were also explored while the thyroid profile was also explored through clinical history, physical examination and specific investigations. The Hamilton depression and anxiety rating scales were used to detect the depression and anxiety whereas the data was collected on pre-designed proforma and analyzed in SPSS to manipulate the frequencies and percentages.

RESULTS:

During six month study period total fifty patients had anxiety and depression was explored and study. The mean $\pm$ SD for age (yrs) of population was 49.88 ± 6.32 . The demographical and clinical profile of study population is presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1: THE DEMOGRAPHICAL AND CLINICAL PROFILE OF STUDY POPULATION

Parameter	Frequency (N=50)	Percentage (%)
AGE (yrs)		
20-29	04	8.0
30-39	07	14
40-49	11	22
50-59	13	26
60-69	09	18
70+	06	12
GENDER		
Male	20	40
Female	30	60
PSYCHIATRIC ILLNESS		
Anxiety	15	30
Depression	13	26
RESIDENCE		
Urban	23	46
Rural	27	54
MARITAL STATUS		
Married	35	70
Single	15	30
DEPRESSION		
Mild	06	46.1
Moderate	04	30.7
Severe	03	23.0
ANXIETY		
Mild	07	46.6
Moderate	06	40.0
Severe	02	13.3

DISCUSSION:

The existence of hypothyroidism is increasingly in females of more established age population. These discoveries are like the aftereffects of the investigation directed by Redmond [29] in 2002 and Chaudhary R, et al [6]. People with hypothyroidism are at a danger of depression and have additionally been recommended by a few authors [7, 8].] Hence, our examination likewise is in concordance with the past information in regards to the comorbidity of discouragement and hypothyroidism as 60%. Ittermann T, et al [7] and Bensenor, IM et al [9] recommended that people with hypothyroidism are at

a danger of anxiety though Cosci F, et al [8] proposed that anxiety is certainly not a typical element co-happening with therapeutic issue. In present survey, the most well-known side effects among guys were mood disturbance (65%) anxiety and genital side effects (71%), a sleeping disorder (30%), and general physical symptoms (69%). Be that as it may, Chaudhary R, et al [6] had additionally the comparable event of these side effects. Thvilum M, et al [10] demonstrated that the patients with hypothyroidism are at expanded danger of being determined to have mental issue both when the analysis of hypothyroidism and being treated with antidepressants, antipsychotics, just as anxiolytics. In this manner, any patient on treatment for hypothyroidism not improving or not ready to achieve premorbid way of life must be screened for gloom and nervousness side effects utilizing any of the rating scales and managed accordingly.

CONCLUSION:

Thyroid hormones assume to be a significant job in state of mind and conduct, and perception is a built up element. In this manner, the relationship between's psychiatry issue and thyroid status is a noteworthy territory of concern.

REFERENCES:

1. Davidoff F, Gill J. Myxedema madness: Psychosis as an early manifestation of hypothyroidism. *Conn Med.* 1977;41:618–21.
2. Gold MS, Pottash AL, Extein I. Hypothyroidism and depression. Evidence from complete thyroid function evaluation. *JAMA.* 1981;245:1919–22.
3. Boral GC, Ghosh AB, Pal SK, Ghosh KK, Nandi DN. Thyroid function in different psychiatric disorders. *Indian J Psychiatry.* 1980;22:200–2.
4. Gupta S, Saha PK, Mukhopadhyay A. Prevalence of hypothyroidism and importance of cholesterol estimation in patients suffering from major depressive disorder. *J Indian Med Assoc.* 2008;106:240–2
5. Whybrow PC, Prange AJ, Treadway CR. Mental changes accompanying thyroid gland dysfunction. A reappraisal using objective psychological measurement. *Arch Gen Psychiatry.* 1969;20:48–63.
6. Chaudhary R, Chabra S, Singla M, Mishra BP, Sharma A. Psychiatric morbidity among hypothyroid patients – A hospital based study. *Delhi Psychiatry J.* 2014;17:35–8
7. Ittermann T, Völzke H, Baumeister SE, Appel K, Grabe HJ. Diagnosed thyroid disorders are associated with depression and anxiety. *Soc Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol.* 2015;50:1417–25
8. Cosci F, Fava GA, Sonino N. Mood and anxiety disorders as early manifestations of medical illness: A systematic review. *PsychotherPsychosom.* 2015;84:22–9.
9. Bensenor IM, Nunes MA, Sander Diniz MF, Santos IS, Brunoni AR, Lotufo PA. Subclinical thyroid dysfunction and psychiatric disorders: Cross-sectional results from the Brazilian Study of Adult Health (ELSA-Brasil) *Clin Endocrinol (Oxf)* 2015;84:250–6.
10. Thvilum M, Brandt F, Almind D, Christensen K, Brix TH, Hegedüs L. Increased psychiatric morbidity before and after the diagnosis of hypothyroidism: A nationwide register study. *Thyroid.* 2014;24:802–8.